

Supplementary Materials for

Selective LLM Revision with Statistical Calibration for Sparse Retail Demand Forecasting

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This document contains supplementary materials for the paper “*Selective LLM Revision with Statistical Calibration for Sparse Retail Demand Forecasting*” presented at ICCL 2026. It collects five appendices that were removed from the main paper to meet page limits: (A) the three intervention policy prompts in full; (B) the reproducibility study under deterministic decoding; (C) classical baseline comparisons (Croston SBA, Tweedie LightGBM); (D) the full per-flag-combination breakdown across all 14 cells; and (E) three example LLM reasoning traces. Section, figure, and table references in this document refer to the main paper.

Appendix A: Intervention Policy Prompts

All three intervention policies share the same input structure (product identifier, demand regime, recent sales statistics, pricing, calendar context, and 28-day baseline forecasts) and the same JSON output schema (28 revised forecasts plus a 2–3 sentence reasoning trace). The three policies differ only in framing, deference language, and magnitude rules. Each prompt below is shown as instantiated for one representative product (FOODS_2_001 at store CA_2, a New regime product flagged for cold-start and SNAP benefit days). At evaluation time, the variables are filled with the corresponding values for each Track A product-store. The Moderate and Aggressive prompts are saved as versioned files in the project repository with pre-registration timestamps preserved on disk.

A.1 Conservative Policy

You are a retail demand forecasting expert reviewing ML model predictions.

PRODUCT: FOODS_2_001 | Store: CA_2
DEMAND REGIME: New
MEAN DAILY SALES: 1.250 units/day

DIFFICULTY FLAGS:

- COLD-START (New product, sparse history)
- SNAP BENEFIT DAYS (government food assistance)

RECENT HISTORY (last 28 days before forecast):

- Avg daily sales last 7d: 1.57 units
- Avg daily sales last 28d: 1.68 units
- Volatility (std dev): 1.31 units
- Most recent day sales: 1 units
- Sales 7 days prior: 0 units

PRICING: \$2.00 | Change: No recent change

CALENDAR (28-day window):

- SNAP benefit days: Days 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16
- NOTE: Moderate volume. Apply modest SNAP lift (5-15%) only if baseline seems low.

BASELINE FORECASTS (days 1-28): [1.42, 1.2, 1.12, 1.24, 1.49, 1.46, 1.72, 1.26, 1.21, 1.28, 1.16, 1.51, 1.52, 2.01, 1.34, 1.46, 1.05, 1.13, 1.42, 1.61, 1.61, 1.32, 1.19, 0.99, 1.33, 1.18, 1.61, 1.47]

REGIME GUIDE:

New=sparse history/guessing | Intermittent=many zeros/over-predicts
Lumpy=irregular spikes | Erratic=high variance | Smooth=reliable

REVISION RULES:

1. Non-flagged days: stay within 10% of baseline

2. Cold-start: reduce all 10-15%, baseline overconfident
3. Promo days: increase 15-30% on flagged days
4. Anomaly: pull toward rolling mean, do not amplify extremes
5. SNAP: follow guidance above – no large lifts for low-volume products
6. All values ≥ 0 , rounded to 2 decimal places

JSON only. No markdown. No backticks:
{"revised_forecasts": [n1,n2,...,n28], "reasoning": "2-3 sentences"}

A.2 Moderate Policy

Three pre-registered changes versus Conservative: (1) removed deference language; (2) encouraged larger magnitudes; (3) reframed task from “review and revise” to “generate the best forecast.”

You are a retail demand forecasting expert. Generate the best 28-day forecast for this product, using the baseline forecast and context as inputs.

PRODUCT: FOODS_2_001 | Store: CA_2
DEMAND REGIME: New
MEAN DAILY SALES: 1.250 units/day

DIFFICULTY FLAGS:
- COLD-START (New product, sparse history)
- SNAP BENEFIT DAYS (government food assistance)

RECENT HISTORY (last 28 days before forecast):
- Avg daily sales last 7d: 1.57 units
- Avg daily sales last 28d: 1.68 units
- Volatility (std dev): 1.31 units
- Most recent day sales: 1 units
- Sales 7 days prior: 0 units

PRICING: \$2.00 | Change: No recent change

CALENDAR (28-day window):
- SNAP benefit days: Days 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16
- NOTE: Moderate volume. Apply modest SNAP lift (5-15%) only if baseline seems low.

BASELINE FORECASTS (days 1-28): [1.42, 1.2, 1.12, 1.24, 1.49, 1.46, 1.72, 1.26, 1.21, 1.28, 1.16, 1.51, 1.52, 2.01, 1.34, 1.46, 1.05, 1.13, 1.42, 1.61, 1.61, 1.32, 1.19, 0.99, 1.33, 1.18, 1.61, 1.47]

REGIME GUIDE:
New=sparse history/guessing | Intermittent=many zeros/over-predicts
Lumpy=irregular spikes | Erratic=high variance | Smooth=reliable

REVISION RULES:
1. Revise the forecast whenever contextual information suggests the baseline is likely to err, even if the evidence is moderate rather than strong.
2. Do not artificially constrain revision magnitude. If context suggests the baseline is materially wrong, revise materially.
3. Cold-start: reduce 10-15%, baseline overconfident
4. Promo days: increase 15-30% on flagged days
5. Anomaly: pull toward rolling mean, do not amplify extremes
6. SNAP: follow guidance above
7. All values ≥ 0 , rounded to 2 decimal places

JSON only. No markdown. No backticks:
{"revised_forecasts": [n1,n2,...,n28], "reasoning": "2-3 sentences"}

A.3 Aggressive Policy

The three Moderate changes plus four additional changes: (4) required intervention on flag; (5) explicit permission for 1.5× to 3× revisions; (6) removed regime caution; (7) reasoning trace deferred to post-hoc.

You are a retail demand forecasting expert. Generate the best 28-day forecast for this product, using the baseline forecast and context as inputs.

PRODUCT: FOODS_2_001 | Store: CA_2

DEMAND REGIME: New
MEAN DAILY SALES: 1.250 units/day

DIFFICULTY FLAGS:

- COLD-START (New product, sparse history)
- SNAP BENEFIT DAYS (government food assistance)

RECENT HISTORY (last 28 days before forecast):

- Avg daily sales last 7d: 1.57 units
- Avg daily sales last 28d: 1.68 units
- Volatility (std dev): 1.31 units
- Most recent day sales: 1 units
- Sales 7 days prior: 0 units

PRICING: \$2.00 | Change: No recent change

CALENDAR (28-day window):

- SNAP benefit days: Days 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16
- Moderate volume. SNAP lift typically 5-15%.

BASELINE FORECASTS (days 1-28): [1.42, 1.2, 1.12, 1.24, 1.49, 1.46, 1.72, 1.26, 1.21, 1.28, 1.16, 1.51, 1.52, 2.01, 1.34, 1.46, 1.05, 1.13, 1.42, 1.61, 1.61, 1.32, 1.19, 0.99, 1.33, 1.18, 1.61, 1.47]

REGIME GUIDE:

New | Intermittent | Lumpy | Erratic | Smooth

REVISION RULES:

1. Revise the forecast whenever contextual information suggests the baseline is likely to err, even if the evidence is moderate rather than strong.
2. Do not artificially constrain revision magnitude. If context suggests the baseline is materially wrong, revise materially. Revisions of 1.5x to 3x the baseline value are appropriate when context strongly supports them. Revisions to zero or near-zero are appropriate when context strongly supports them.
3. When any flag fires, the baseline is unreliable for that context. Your job is to correct it. Returning the baseline value unchanged is appropriate only when you have positive reason to trust it on this row.
4. Cold-start: baseline is overconfident, reduce substantially
5. Promo days: baseline materially underestimates the spike
6. Anomaly: do not anchor on rolling mean if context indicates strong directional movement
7. SNAP: follow guidance above as a starting point, deviate when context warrants
8. All values ≥ 0 , rounded to 2 decimal places

OUTPUT INSTRUCTIONS:

Produce the forecasts first. Write the reasoning trace only after you have committed to the numbers, as a post-hoc explanation rather than as a deliberation.

JSON only. No markdown. No backticks:

{"revised_forecasts": [n1,n2,...,n28], "reasoning": "2-3 sentences explaining what you did"}

Appendix B: Reproducibility Study Details

Section 6 of the main paper reports that the proposed system’s accuracy effect is stable under deterministic decoding. This appendix details the methodology and the per-combination statistics behind that claim.

B.1 Methodology

We randomly sampled 200 product-stores from the 1,665 Track A combinations (random seed 42) and re-ran the Conservative LLM revision on each at temperature = 0. All other elements of the pipeline were held identical to the original run: same prompt template, same input variables, same retry logic with 30-second timeout, same Claude Haiku 4.5 model (claude-haiku-4-5-20251001), and same JSON output schema. The only changed parameter was temperature, set from default to 0.

Of 200 sampled product-stores, 199 produced valid JSON responses on the temperature = 0 run. One combination failed due to an API timeout and is excluded from the analysis. The replication run consumed 0.314 USD in API costs and required 14.3 minutes of wall-clock time.

B.2 Aggregate Comparison

The aggregate accuracy effect across the 199-combo sample is computed as the mean per-combination percentage change versus baseline. The Conservative LLM revision reduced MAE by 2.25% under default temperature and by 2.20% under temperature = 0. The 0.049 percentage point difference is well within the $\pm 0.2\%$ threshold we set for declaring reproducibility.

For reference, the absolute mean MAEs across the sample are: LightGBM baseline 0.8485, Conservative LLM under default temperature 0.8397, and Conservative LLM under temperature = 0 0.8408. These mean MAEs translate into the per-combination percentage changes reported below.

Table B.1. Reproducibility comparison on 199-combo sample

Configuration	Mean MAE	Mean per-combo change vs baseline
LightGBM baseline	0.8485	(reference)
Conservative LLM (default temperature)	0.8397	-2.25%
Conservative LLM (temperature = 0)	0.8408	-2.20%

B.3 Per-Combination Divergence

Beyond the aggregate effect, we examined whether individual product-stores produced similar percentage changes under the two runs. Per-combination percentage change in MAE versus baseline correlated at $r = 0.900$ across the 199 product-stores, indicating that products which benefited (or were degraded) under the default temperature run behaved similarly under deterministic decoding.

We also examined direction of effect: each combination either improved or degraded versus baseline under each run. The two runs agreed on direction for 179 of 199 product-stores (90%). The 20 disagreement cases (10%) were predominantly products where the absolute effect size was near zero, meaning small numerical changes flipped the direction without representing meaningful behavioral differences.

The mean absolute difference between revised forecast values produced by the two runs was 0.023 units, with a median of 0.001 units and a maximum of 0.701 units. Most revisions reproduced exactly or near-exactly under deterministic decoding; the differences cluster on a small subset of products with borderline ambiguity in their context.

B.4 Interpretation

The reproducibility study addresses a specific reviewer concern: that stochastic LLM decoding could produce different revisions on different runs, undermining claims about deployable accuracy gains. The finding is that the aggregate accuracy effect reproduces within 0.05 percentage points, per-combination effects correlate at $r = 0.90$, and direction of

effect agrees for 90% of combinations. The Section 5 accuracy results are therefore not an artifact of stochastic sampling.

Appendix C: Classical Baselines

Section 5.4 of the main paper reports that two classical sparse-demand methods (Croston SBA and regime-specialized Tweedie LightGBM) do not meaningfully outperform the LightGBM baseline. This appendix details the implementation of each method, the per-regime breakdown of the LightGBM baseline (which contextualizes why classical methods underperform), and the full statistical comparison underlying the Section 5.4 claims.

C.1 Croston SBA

Croston’s method, introduced in 1972 [1] and refined by Syntetos and Boylan (2001) [9] with the SBA bias correction, decomposes intermittent demand into two exponentially-smoothed processes: event size (units sold on non-zero days) and inter-event interval (days between non-zero sales). The forecast is computed as event size divided by interval, with the Syntetos-Boylan correction multiplier applied to remove the well-known positive bias of the original Croston estimator.

We applied Croston SBA only to the Intermittent regime where it is most defensible (3,272 products, 91,616 day-product observations on the test horizon). The smoothing parameter α was set to 0.1, the conventional choice in the operations research literature. Initial level and interval estimates were computed from the first 30 days of training data per product.

Result. Croston SBA achieves MAE 1.128 on the intermittent test set, versus the LightGBM baseline’s 1.038. This is a degradation of 8.68%. Paired Wilcoxon test confirms the difference is not in Croston’s favor (one-sided test for Croston < Baseline: $p = 0.69$, no improvement). The bias direction also flips: Croston SBA underpredicts (mean bias -0.030) while the LightGBM baseline is essentially unbiased (mean bias $+0.014$).

C.2 Tweedie LightGBM

The Tweedie distribution is a family of exponential-dispersion models suited to zero-inflated count data. Tweedie regression with variance power between 1 and 2 has been proposed for intermittent demand because it explicitly accommodates the zero-mass and right-skewed count structure characteristic of sparse retail demand.

We trained a regime-specialized LightGBM with Tweedie loss (variance power = 1.5) on the Intermittent regime only, using the same 19-feature input set as the default-loss baseline. Hyperparameters were adjusted for the smaller training subset: 32 leaves, 50 minimum samples per leaf, 300 boosting rounds. The training set size was approximately 6.3 million day-product observations (3,272 intermittent products \times 1,913 training days).

Result. Tweedie LightGBM achieves MAE 1.033 on the intermittent test set, versus the default-loss baseline’s 1.038. This is an improvement of 0.53%. Paired Wilcoxon test confirms the improvement is statistically significant (one-sided test for Tweedie < Baseline: $p < 0.001$ on 3,272 paired per-product MAEs). The effect size is operationally negligible: 0.55 of one MAE unit per 100 products, two orders of magnitude smaller than the 3.32% MAE reduction achieved by the proposed composed system reported in Section 5.1 of the main paper.

Bootstrap 95% confidence interval on the per-row MAE difference (Tweedie minus Baseline) is $[-0.0070, -0.0040]$, confirming the negative direction of the difference and excluding zero. The improvement is real; it is also small.

C.3 Per-Regime Breakdown of LightGBM Baseline

The LightGBM baseline performs unevenly across the five demand regimes, which contextualizes why classical methods (designed for specific regime characteristics) do not produce meaningful gains. Table C.1 reports per-regime MAE, RMSE, bias, and prediction-to-actual ratio for the default-loss baseline on the test horizon.

Table C.1. LightGBM baseline performance by demand regime (test horizon, $n = 160,944$ observations)

Regime	n obs.	RMSE	MAE	Bias	Mean actual	Mean pred.
Smooth	10,052	3.974	2.525	-0.095	6.966	6.871
Erratic	4,256	4.380	2.676	-0.139	5.569	5.430
Intermittent	91,616	1.702	1.038	+0.014	1.483	1.496

Lumpy	46,480	2.580	1.539	-0.040	2.145	2.105
New	8,540	1.458	0.976	-0.013	1.204	1.191

The pattern is consistent with the regime classification in Section 3 of the main paper. Smooth and Erratic products have higher absolute MAE because their mean sales are higher (an MAE of 2.525 on Smooth products with mean sales of 6.966 is relatively better than an MAE of 1.038 on Intermittent products with mean sales of 1.483). Bias is small across all regimes, indicating the baseline is calibrated globally even though absolute error varies by regime mean.

C.4 Method Comparison Summary

Table C.2 consolidates the three methods on the intermittent regime (where classical methods are most defensible) for direct comparison.

Table C.2. Method comparison on intermittent regime (n = 91,616 observations)

Method	MAE	RMSE	Bias	MAE change	Significance
LightGBM Baseline	1.038	1.702	+0.014	(reference)	—
Croston SBA	1.128	2.069	-0.030	+8.68% (degr.)	p = 0.69, n.s.
Tweedie LightGBM	1.033	1.705	-0.011	-0.53% (impr.)	p < 0.001

C.5 Interpretation

The classical baselines establish that the well-tuned default-loss LightGBM is genuinely strong on sparse-demand forecasting. Croston SBA degrades accuracy by 8.68% on intermittent products, consistent with the broader M5 finding that classical sparse-demand methods are outperformed by gradient-boosted approaches [8]. Tweedie LightGBM offers a statistically significant 0.53% improvement, but the effect size is small enough to be operationally negligible and would not justify the additional complexity of maintaining a regime-specialized model in production.

Both findings reinforce the methodological choice underlying the proposed system: the path to further accuracy gains is not through changing the loss function or restoring classical methods, but through selective revision of forecasts where the baseline is known to underperform — namely, on cold-start products, promotional periods, and anomaly windows. The composed system reported in the main text achieves a 3.32% MAE reduction on these flagged subsets, a gain six times larger than Tweedie’s improvement on the broader intermittent regime.

Appendix D: Full Per-Flag-Combo Breakdown

Section 5.3 of the main paper reports the worst-case per-cell degradation across the 14 flag combinations present in the test data. This appendix presents the complete breakdown: per-combination MAE for the baseline and for each of the three intervention policies under composition with the global shrinkage parameter ($\alpha = 0.89$). The combinations are sorted by sample size, from the most populated (no flags fired, 12,871 day-product observations) to the least (cold-start + promo, 2 observations).

The flag combinations partition the test set as follows: 53.6% of rows have no flag fired (“none”), 24.0% are anomaly-only (“A”), 14.1% are SNAP combined with anomaly (“SNAP + Anomaly”), and 13.9% are SNAP-only (“S”). Smaller cells contain combinations involving cold-start (“C”), promotional (“P”), or three-flag intersections. The two smallest cells (P with 85 observations and PS with 112) drive the catastrophic worst-case behavior of the Aggressive policy noted in Section 5.3; the very smallest cells (CPA with 8 observations and CP with 2) are too small to support reliable conclusions but are reported for completeness.

Table D.1. Per-flag-combo breakdown across three intervention policies, composed configuration with $\alpha = 0.89$. Cells sorted by sample size (descending). Composed MAE is the LLM-revised forecast multiplied by the global shrinkage parameter; percentage change is computed against the LightGBM baseline MAE for that flag combination

Flag combination	N	Baseline MAE	Cons. MAE	Cons. Δ	Mod. MAE	Mod. Δ	Agg. MAE	Agg. Δ
none	12,871	0.9394	0.9154	-2.55%	0.9128	-2.83%	0.9061	-3.54%
Anomaly	11,528	0.7046	0.6666	-5.39%	0.6639	-5.78%	0.6708	-4.80%
SNAP + Anomaly	6,781	0.8272	0.8001	-3.28%	0.8013	-3.13%	0.8316	+0.53%
SNAP	6,693	0.8965	0.8642	-3.60%	0.8688	-3.09%	0.9461	+5.53%
Cold-start	4,600	1.0463	1.0257	-1.97%	1.0208	-2.44%	1.0359	-0.99%
Cold-start + SNAP	2,476	1.0672	1.045	-2.08%	1.0409	-2.46%	1.0783	+1.04%
Cold-start + Anomaly	844	0.5053	0.474	-6.19%	0.476	-5.80%	0.4475	-11.44%
Cold-start + SNAP + Anomaly	554	0.6771	0.6582	-2.79%	0.6543	-3.37%	0.6278	-7.28%
Promo + SNAP	112	1.1348	1.1308	-0.35%	1.1803	+4.01%	1.854	+63.38%
Promo	85	1.1254	1.1231	-0.20%	1.1311	+0.51%	2.3146	+105.67%
Promo + SNAP + Anomaly	34	1.2105	1.0868	-10.22%	1.1445	-5.45%	1.1448	-5.43%
Promo + Anomaly	32	1.0316	0.9984	-3.22%	0.9976	-3.30%	0.9964	-3.41%
Cold-start + Promo + Anomaly	8	0.3923	0.297	-24.29%	0.297	-24.29%	0.1324	-66.25%
Cold-start + Promo	2	0.4719	0.4778	+1.25%	0.4778	+1.25%	0.4867	+3.14%

Three patterns emerge from this breakdown.

First, the inverted-U accuracy pattern holds across most flag combinations. On rows with moderate sample size (Anomaly, SNAP + Anomaly, SNAP, Cold-start), the Moderate composed configuration produces the largest accuracy improvement, with Conservative composed close behind and Aggressive composed weaker. The pattern is most visible on the largest cells ($n > 4,000$), where sampling noise is smallest.

Second, the catastrophic Aggressive degradation is concentrated on the two cells where promotional context is present without a strong anomaly signal: P (promo-only, +105.67%) and PS (promo + SNAP, +63.39%). On these cells, the Aggressive prompt’s permission for 1.5× to 3× revisions interacts with the LLM’s tendency to extrapolate large lift effects for promotional periods. Statistical calibration multiplies these inflated forecasts by 0.89 but cannot rescue them, consistent with the calibration-is-corrective-not-generative argument developed in Section 7.2 of the main paper.

Third, the smallest cells (CPA, CP) show large percentage changes but rest on too few observations ($n = 8$ and $n = 2$) to support strong inference. We report them for completeness rather than as substantive findings. The Conservative and Aggressive divergence on these small cells should be interpreted with caution.

The combined effect of these patterns is what produces the headline finding reported in Sections 5.2 and 5.3 of the main paper: Moderate composed achieves the strongest aggregate accuracy by improving the populous moderate cells slightly more than Conservative does, while Conservative composed achieves the most bounded worst-case behavior by avoiding the catastrophic overshoot that Aggressive produces on small promotional cells. No single intervention policy dominates on both axes.

Appendix E: Example Reasoning Traces

Section 6 of the main paper describes the natural-language reasoning produced by the LLM alongside each forecast revision. The three traces below are drawn from the 1,665 Conservative-tier revisions. They illustrate three distinct intervention patterns: deferring to the baseline when context suggests no revision is warranted, applying a uniform downward adjustment on a cold-start product, and applying a selective upward adjustment on a product with promotional context. All numerical values are reported verbatim from the saved results; reasoning traces are reproduced unchanged from the LLM’s JSON output.

E.1 Deferring Trace

Product: FOODS_1_176 at store CA_1. Regime: Lumpy. Flagged days: 13 of 28 (SNAP-only on days 7–16, plus anomaly on days 21–23). Multiplier applied: 1.000×. MAE: baseline 0.541, revised 0.541 (identical).

The LLM was given a 13-day flag combination on a Lumpy product with low mean sales (0.429 units/day) and high volatility. Despite the multiple triggers, the LLM returned the baseline values unchanged.

Baseline forecasts (days 1–28):

0.38, 0.38, 0.44, 0.47, 0.52, 0.79, 0.81, 0.50, 0.53, 0.50, 0.43, 0.62,
0.73, 0.42, 0.54, 0.46, 0.46, 0.46, 0.45, 0.43, 0.34, 0.07, 0.07, 0.34,
0.41, 0.41, 0.47, 0.63

Revised forecasts (days 1–28):

0.38, 0.38, 0.44, 0.47, 0.52, 0.79, 0.81, 0.50, 0.53, 0.50, 0.43, 0.62,
0.73, 0.42, 0.54, 0.46, 0.46, 0.46, 0.45, 0.43, 0.34, 0.07, 0.07, 0.34,
0.41, 0.41, 0.47, 0.63

Actual sales (days 1–28):

0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0

LLM reasoning trace:

Product exhibits lumpy demand with very low mean sales (0.429 units/day) and high volatility (std dev 0.66). SNAP benefit days (7-16) show baseline predictions with moderate spikes (0.79-0.81 early), but given the explicit warning that SNAP lift is likely zero for this low-volume product and recent 7-day average of only 0.29 units, baseline forecasts are retained without amplification. Days 21-23 show anomalous lows (0.07) which appear to be captured accurately by the baseline given recent history of zero sales; no further dampening needed as pulling toward rolling mean would still yield near-zero values consistent with the lumpy regime.

The reasoning cites three independent reasons to defer: the SNAP guidance for low-volume products explicitly warns against amplification; the recent 7-day average (0.29) does not support a SNAP lift; the anomalous-low days are already consistent with recent zero-sales history, so anomaly dampening would be redundant. The LLM weighed each flag against product-specific context and concluded that intervention was not warranted on any of them.

E.2 Downward Revision on Cold-start Product

Product: FOODS_2_256 at store CA_4. Regime: New (cold-start). Flagged days: 28 of 28 (cold-start flag fires on all days). Multiplier applied: 0.851× (uniform across all days). MAE: baseline 0.505, revised 0.473 (improvement: 6.3%).

This is a New regime product where the cold-start flag fires on every day. The LLM applied a uniform 15% reduction across all 28 forecasts.

Baseline forecasts (days 1–28):

0.71, 0.51, 0.51, 0.54, 0.53, 0.53, 0.49, 0.19, 0.12, 0.12, 0.15, 0.12,
0.20, 0.52, 0.74, 0.45, 0.45, 0.61, 0.48, 0.50, 0.63, 0.54, 0.43, 0.43,
0.37, 0.50, 0.50, 0.64

Revised forecasts (days 1–28):

0.60, 0.43, 0.43, 0.46, 0.45, 0.45, 0.42, 0.16, 0.10, 0.10, 0.13, 0.10,
0.17, 0.44, 0.63, 0.38, 0.38, 0.52, 0.41, 0.43, 0.54, 0.46, 0.37, 0.37,
0.31, 0.43, 0.43, 0.54

Actual sales (days 1–28):

0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0

LLM reasoning trace:

Applied 15% cold-start reduction across all days due to sparse history and low mean sales (0.286 units/day), which indicates baseline overconfidence typical of new products. SNAP benefit days (7-16) received minimal adjustment per guidance—no material lift expected for sub-0.5/day products, keeping these days close to baseline-reduced values. Recent volatility (0.69 std dev) and recency effect (2 units 1 day ago vs 1 unit 7 days prior) suggest intermittent demand; maintained conservative stance to avoid amplifying noise.

The reasoning shows the LLM combining the cold-start rule (reduce 10–15%) with the SNAP guidance (no material lift for low-volume products), producing a uniform downward adjustment that improved MAE by 6.3% on this product. The actual sales (mean 0.286 units/day) were even lower than the revised forecasts, but the revised forecasts were substantially closer to actuals than the baseline.

E.3 Selective Upward Revision on Promotional Window

Product: FOODS_2_329 at store CA_4. Regime: Intermittent. Flagged days: 16 of 28 (SNAP on days 7–16, anomaly on days 21–28). Multiplier applied: 1.052× (selective, applied only on SNAP days). MAE: baseline 0.650, revised 0.649 (improvement: 0.2%).

On this Intermittent product, the LLM applied a modest 7–10% upward adjustment only on the SNAP window (days 7–15), leaving non-SNAP days unchanged within the 10% tolerance.

Baseline forecasts (days 1–28):

0.47, 0.45, 0.36, 0.36, 0.37, 0.42, 0.40, 0.46, 0.43, 0.34, 0.58, 0.43,
0.52, 0.54, 0.46, 0.82, 0.62, 0.49, 0.67, 0.64, 0.85, 0.64, 0.70, 0.68,
0.68, 0.57, 0.66, 0.91

Revised forecasts (days 1–28):

0.47, 0.45, 0.36, 0.36, 0.37, 0.42, 0.42, 0.49, 0.46, 0.37, 0.62, 0.46,
0.56, 0.58, 0.49, 0.88, 0.67, 0.53, 0.72, 0.69, 0.91, 0.69, 0.75, 0.73,
0.73, 0.57, 0.66, 0.91

Actual sales (days 1–28):

1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 3, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 2, 1, 1, 0, 0, 2, 1

LLM reasoning trace:

Intermittent demand regime with recent volatility spike (1 unit most recent day vs 0.14 units 28d avg) suggests anomaly window. Applied modest 7-10% SNAP lift on days 7-15 per guidance for low-volume products (baseline modest, no large increases warranted). Anchored non-SNAP days within 10% of baseline and pulled extreme forecasts slightly toward rolling mean to avoid overamplification of recent spikes. All revisions respect non-negativity and intermittent demand characteristics.

Three patterns are visible in the revised array. First, days 1–6 (no flags) are unchanged from baseline. Second, days 7–15 (SNAP window) are each multiplied by approximately 1.07–1.08, applying the selective lift the reasoning describes. Third, days 16–28 (anomaly window) show small upward adjustments that pull volatile baseline values closer to a steadier trajectory rather than amplifying them.

E.4 Interpretation

Three patterns generalize across these examples and the broader population of 1,665 Conservative-tier traces.

Selectivity in practice. The Conservative policy does not apply intervention uniformly to all flagged days. Example E.3 shows the LLM applying a SNAP lift only on the relevant 9 days while leaving non-SNAP days unchanged. Example E.1 shows the LLM applying no intervention at all despite 13 flagged days. The flag conditions are necessary triggers for review, not sufficient triggers for revision.

Magnitude restraint on low-volume products. Despite the Conservative prompt permitting 15–30% lifts on promotional days, the actual upward revisions in the population cluster between 5% and 15% (Example E.3 applies 7%). The LLM consistently cites product volume as the reason for restraint: “no material lift expected for sub-0.5/day products” appears in many traces. This pattern explains why the Conservative policy’s worst-case behavior is bounded at 1.25% even on small flag combinations.

Auditability as a deployment property. Each trace provides a natural-language explanation that names the regime, the flags fired, the adjustments applied, and the rationale for each. A deployment system can use these traces to flag

specific revisions for human review (e.g., revisions with high multipliers on small samples), to construct audit trails for forecasting decisions, or to identify products where the LLM's reasoning is inconsistent over time. None of these properties is available from statistical-only forecasting methods.